

Policy concerning the use of Generative AI at the Netherlands eScience Center

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Part 1: Provisions for Netherlands eScience Center personnel

The following provisions pre-empt a more comprehensive policy to be defined in the coming months:

- *Experimentation with, and investigation of the potential of, Generative AI* (for example: ChatGPT for generating text data, Copilot for generating prototype software, or Midjourney for generating image data) by all eScience Center employees is allowed and explicitly encouraged.
- *The use of Generative AI* in the creation of documents (or other forms of output, incl. presentations, blog posts, software, etcetera) intended for internal or external *sharing or publication* is permitted, but – given the many technological, ethical, social and legal uncertainties and pitfalls – not explicitly encouraged.
- When using Generative AI in the creation of a document (or other form of output, incl. software) intended for internal or external sharing or publication:
 - o it is important to first understand and consider the inherent limitations and drawbacks of using Generative AI (e.g: unreliability, potential bias, obsolescence, potential plagiarism, lack of authenticity, lack of transparency, hidden costs); specifically in the case of software, AI generated code should be considered faulty, untrustworthy, insecure, potentially malicious, inefficient and licensed incorrectly, until proven otherwise;
 - o it is important to realize that the publisher of AI generated output is ultimately responsible, as if the output was entirely created by her/himself; apart from the individual responsibility of each eScience Center employee, all line managers have a responsibility in instructing their teams as well as possible;
 - o it is obligatory to verify the correctness, accuracy and completeness of the AI-generated output¹; if the need arises, adaptations to the AI-generated output must be made - also in cases where the AI-generated output is overly uniform, non-authentic, or otherwise misaligned with existing eScience Center output.
 - o to ensure full transparency, and in support of the principles of open science, it is obligatory to explicitly indicate which parts of your output have been AI-assisted and/or AI-generated, and by which Generative AI tool (incl. version number, if available and relevant); although proper legislation is still lacking, failing to do so may be an offense similar to, or bordering on, plagiarism or fraud.

A typical reference to AI-generated data could be as follows:

“The above text/section/software code/image... has been generated and/or refined using <named Generative AI> (version <number>). All AI-output has been verified for correctness, accuracy and completeness, adapted where needed, and approved by the author.”

¹ Note that this does *not* imply verification of (the inner workings of) the applied AI tool itself. After all, this would be – in most cases – quite impossible.

- The use of Generative AI, and the internal or external sharing or publication of AI-generated output, is strictly forbidden²
 - o in cases where privacy-sensitive, organization-critical, or otherwise confidential data could leak outside of predetermined or intended boundaries;
 - o in cases where the correctness, accuracy and completeness of the AI-generated output has not been, or cannot be, verified¹;
 - o in cases where AI-generated software has not been, or cannot be, tested rigorously;
 - o in cases where questions of copyright or software licensing may arise;
 - o in cases where ethical boundaries may be crossed;
 - o in cases where (inter)national laws and regulations may be violated.

In case of doubt, or in case any of the above provisions is too restrictive for the proper execution of your work, please inform the contact persons below. If sufficiently justified, and if not in conflict with prevailing laws and regulations, exceptions to the above provisions may be approved by the Directors Team.

- When submitting an article or proposal for publication or review, the provisions outlined in the current policy precede any of the receiver's (e.g. publisher's, funder's, conference's) policies on the acceptable and responsible use of Generative AI. In other words, the current eScience Center policy must be followed first. Only then any provisions applicable in the review and/or publication process must be followed, but only in as much as these do not conflict with the eScience Center's policy.

Given the rapid technological and legal developments, the above provisions may be extended and adapted regularly.

For questions or suggestions related to the provisions in Part 1 of this document, please contact:

- Frank Seinstra, Policy Officer (all topics);
- Patrick Bos, Technology Lead (all software-related topics).

² Note that these provisions do not supersede existing (inter)national laws or regulations. In fact, stronger versions of these provisions may be covered by said laws and regulations and should therefore be adhered to at all times.

Part 2: Provisions for Netherlands eScience Center call procedures

- The use of Generative AI technologies in the preparation of any of the documents which together form a Project Application for submission in a Call for Proposals published by the Netherlands eScience Center is permitted, provided that this use
 - o follows prevailing guidelines and best practices with respect to the acceptable and responsible use of Generative AI technologies, and
 - o complies with existing European and (inter)national legislation (where applicable).
- When using Generative AI technologies in the preparation of a Project Application, authors are advised to understand and consider the possible limitations and drawbacks of the applied AI technologies, including unreliability, potential bias, obsolescence, potential plagiarism, lack of authenticity, lack of transparency, hidden costs.
- Following the principles of Open Science, when using Generative AI technologies in the preparation of a Project Application, authors are required to disclose this use properly. Specifically, it is required:
 - o to include a statement in the main Project Proposal document, as follows:

“In the preparation of this Project Application, parts of the provided texts have been generated and/or refined using <named Generative AI> (version <number>). All AI-output has been verified for correctness, accuracy and completeness, revised where needed, and approved by the author(s).”*

(*in case multiple Generative AI technologies have been used, this should be indicated).
 - o to provide information on the specific role Generative AI has played in preparing the Project Application, the extent to which Generative AI has been used, and the reasons why.
- If disclosed properly, the use of Generative AI in a Project Application, in itself, has no positive or negative impact on the evaluation of the Application. All peer reviewers and all members of the Evaluation Committee will be instructed to simply assume the Application is written by the authors in its entirety.
- In case it is found – at any phase in the review and evaluation process – that Generative AI has been used in the preparation of a Project Application, while this was not properly disclosed, the Application will not be eligible for funding.
- To ensure confidentiality, and to protect the intellectual rights of the authors, all peer reviewers and all members of the Evaluation Committee will be informed that the use of Generative AI in the review and evaluation of all Project Applications submitted in any Call for Proposals published by the Netherlands eScience Center is strictly forbidden. Also, the Netherlands eScience Center itself will not use Generative AI in its evaluation and review procedures.

For questions related to the provisions in Part 2 of this document, please contact the Netherlands eScience Center Programme Management:

- Tel.: +31 (0)20 460 4770
- Email: open-calls@esciencecenter.nl